

TOUGH BIO-INSPIRED CERAMIC COMPOSITES FOR AMBIENT AND HIGH TEMPERATURE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic materials are excellent candidates for harsh environment applications (e.g., high temperature applications). However, ceramics often suffer from brittle failure, which limit their applications where a potential for mechanical or thermal shocks may exist (e.g. in space applications). Modification of existing ceramic materials based on bioinspired approaches is considered as a solution to address the brittleness of ceramics. Many natural materials demonstrate a ductile behaviour while mainly composed of brittle mineral building blocks. These brittle blocks, often arranged in well-defined architectures, offer high stiffness and strength while weak interfaces between these blocks often provide toughness. In this study, inspired by natural materials, a simple, yet scalable procedure, based on laser-engraving and assembly is employed to fabricate architected ceramic panels with enhanced toughness behaviour. These panels are subjected to impact loading tests. It is found that the architected panels demonstrate more energy absorption compared to plain ceramic panels. This comes at an expense of a decrease in stiffness and strength. The results reveal that the improved performance is rooted in relative sliding of neighbouring tiles which in turn results in frictional energy dissipation, a mechanism which is absent in plain ceramics. Motivated by architected ceramics tested at an ambient temperature, a finite element analysis code, ANSYS Workbench, is used to model thermal shock of 1-layer architected ceramics to better understand their behaviour under sudden temperature changes, a phenomenon which frequently occurs in space applications of ceramic panels. The results suggest that the hexagonal architected ceramics with 10 mm hexagonal blocks absorb more energy and deform less under thermal shocks in comparison to the baseline and other architectures with different building blocks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic materials possess excellent thermal stability, high stiffness and strength, low density and high oxidation/corrosion resistance [1]. This makes them particularly interesting for applications in harsh environmental conditions (e.g., high temperature applications) including exhausts and engines. Despite of these advantages, ceramics generally suffer from brittle fracture behavior which limit their range of applications where a combination of structural reliability and high toughness are required specifically at elevated temperature environment. Given that nature has optimized biological structural materials as functionally efficient configurations, an inspiration from natural materials could address the main drawback of ceramics (i.e., brittleness). Nature, for example in tooth enamel [2] and sea shells [3], has overcome brittleness of ceramics by using stiff and strong architected building blocks with weak interfaces [4]. The concept of architecture and weak interfaces are also used by from ancient times in stone walls, arches, domes [5, 6] and Lamellar armors [7] to recently developed categories of bio-inspired architected materials with unique combination of strength and toughness [1, 8-10].

Architected ceramics reveal unique mechanical properties, such as high indentation resistance [11], failure resistance [12], fracture toughness [13], yield strength [14, 15] and thermal stability [1]. The architectures of these materials could make these structures ideal for applications such as high power transducers [16], high temperature applications [17] and sound absorbers [18]. The

architected ceramics have also been studied for thermal shock behaviour [19], damage resistance [1] and flexural stiffness [8]. The studies on bio-inspired ceramic materials are limited to transparent ceramics (i.e., glass) with applications targeted in ambient temperature.

In this study, by laser engraving of plain ceramic sheets, the concepts of engineered architecture with weak interfaces in multilayered ceramics are demonstrated. The dynamic energy absorption capability of architected ceramics at ambient temperatures and the shock resistance capability of these architected panels at elevated temperatures are investigated using a combination of experimental assessment and numerical simulations. The architectures of multilayered ceramic panels, varied with different geometries for the laser-engraved tiles including hexagonal blocks with three different characteristic lengths are examined.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Design and Fabrication

The multilayered architected ceramic panels were manufactured by the lamination of laser-engraved architected ceramic sheets using Surlyn resin [20]. The architected ceramic sheets and Surlyn resin were stuck up with a specific shift using a vacuum bag to fabricate architected ceramic panels to be kept in oven for 5 hours at temperature up to 146 °C. For fabrication of thin architected ceramic sheets, a 2D laser was used to create the architected design based on hexagonal building blocks as shown in Fig. 1. The design of hexagonal tiles comprised three different characteristic lengths ($L_1 = 2.5, 5$ and 10 mm). We also manufactured multilayered ceramic panels without any architecture with the same procedure mentioned above, called multilayered plain ceramics or baseline, as a reference to compare with multilayered hexagonal ceramics. The overall dimensions of the panels were maintained with $L \times L = 100 \times 100$ mm² and thickness of $h = 2.73$ mm for 4-layer ceramics with adhesion layers. An example of fabricated samples are given in Fig 2.

Figure 1: Schematic figure of the staggered design engraved in the ceramic sheet.

Hexagonal ($L_1 = 10$ mm)

Figure 2: Laser-engraved ceramic sheets and multilayered architected ceramic panels.

2.2. Experimental Test Configurations

Figure 3 presents the configuration and boundary conditions of multi-layer ceramic panels under the low-velocity impact loads. The low-velocity impact tests were performed using a drop weight machine based on the guidelines given in the ASTM standard D3763 [21]. The impactor had a mass of 12 kg and a diameter of 5 mm with a semi-spherical tip. During the impact test, the specimens were free and there was a 76.2 mm diameter hole in the centre of fixture along the moving path of the impactor.

Figure 3: Low-velocity impact test configuration for energy absorption analysis of multilayered architected ceramic panels.

2.3. Finite Element Modelling

A nonlinear finite element analysis (FEA) code, ANSYS, was used to better understand mechanisms that govern the deformation and the energy absorption of single-layer architected ceramics. Four different combinations of architected ceramic panels including three hexagonal designs and a plain configuration were studied. The ceramic panels were meshed with quadrilateral and triangular elements; a convergence study was conducted to avoid mesh size dependency of FEA results. The ceramic was modelled as a linear elastic material with an elastic modulus of 300 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.21. The ceramic tiles were modelled in frictional contacts with the neighbouring tiles (friction coefficients = 0.36).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Mechanical Impact Performance

For experiments, the 4-layer architected ceramic panels were subjected to a 14J low-velocity impact test. Figure 4 illustrates the experimental results for the stiffness, maximum load and energy absorption of architected panels with four different architectures (three hexagonal configurations) and the plain ceramic panel. Figure 4 shows that the hexagonal architected panel with $L_1 = 10$ mm absorbs up to 10% more energy compared to the plain panel. Figure 4a shows that this improvement in the energy absorption performance is decreasing by decreasing the tile sizes. The panel with smaller hexagonal design, however, offers more damage containment, which can contribute to multi-hit capability and/or thermal fatigue resistance. Multilayered hexagonal ceramic panels have lower maximum contact loads compared to the multilayered plain ceramic panel.

3.2. Thermal Performance

Figure 5 presents the temperature distributions of architected ceramics when subjected to a thermal shock, in which the centre of specimens exposed to 1000°C in a 1 second time span for three hexagonal designs and the plain configuration (or baseline). Except for the hexagonal ceramic with $L_1 = 10$ mm, no difference was observed for the temperature distributions in different specimens. Figure 6 displays the maximum frictional stress vs. temperature for architected ceramics. It is seen that the

maximum frictional stress of hexagonal architected ceramic with $L_1 = 2.5$ mm is greater than the others. This was expected since there are more contacts areas in the hexagonal architected ceramic with $L_1 = 2.5$ mm and it can be concluded that the magnitude of frictional energy dissipation is higher than the other architectures (i.e., $L_1 = 5$ and 10 mm). The maximum deformation vs. temperature for architected and plain ceramics is presented in Fig. 7. Maximum deformations were occurred in the centre of all panels due the thermal shock. The baseline shows much larger deformation in comparison to architected ceramics. This can be due to existence of sliding motions in architected ceramics and consequently, the ceramics tiles deform less. This reduction in displacements and/or strains is associated to the reduction of thermal stresses for architected ceramics as compared to the baseline specimen. This offers a favourable trend for reducing thermal shocks in architected ceramics.

Figure 4: Impact properties of the multilayered architected ceramics including hexagonal ($L_1 = 2.5, 5$ and 10 mm) and the plain configuration (baseline).

Figure 5: Temperature distributions of architected ceramics under a central 1000 °C thermal shock.

Figure 6: Maximum frictional stress vs. temperature for architected ceramics.

Figure 7: Maximum deformation vs. temperature for architected and plain ceramics.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Ceramic materials possess excellent properties (high hardness, high chemical/oxidation resistance, high stiffness/strength and relatively low density) which have made them an ideal candidate for applications in extreme environments. The brittleness of ceramics has, however, significantly limited

their use. This paper presents a bio-inspired approach to address this issue which can significantly diversify applications of ceramics more specifically for applications in which a combination of thermal and mechanical shocks is required. In this study, we developed a manufacturing technique to fabricate multilayered architected ceramics. The results suggest that the multilayered architected ceramics offer structural properties considerably different than the baseline ceramics with lower stiffness and higher energy absorption capabilities. We also performed a simple nonlinear FEA which is capable of analyzing dynamic thermal loads to investigate effects of different architectures on energy absorption performance. This proposes a route to develop ceramics with enhanced thermal shock resistance as required in several applications including space.

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References

- [1] G. Karambelas, S. Santhanam, Z.N. Wing, *Strombus gigas* inspired biomimetic ceramic composites via SHELL—Sequential Hierarchical Engineered Layer Lamination, *Ceramics International* 39(2) (2013) 1315-1325.
- [2] S. Habelitz, S. Marshall, G. Marshall Jr, M. Balooch, Mechanical properties of human dental enamel on the nanometre scale, *Archives of Oral Biology* 46(2) (2001) 173-183.
- [3] S. Kamat, X. Su, R. Ballarini, A. Heuer, Structural basis for the fracture toughness of the shell of the conch *Strombus gigas*, *Nature* 405(6790) (2000) 1036-1040.
- [4] M.A. Meyers, P.Y. Chen, A.Y.M. Lin, Y. Seki, Biological materials: Structure and mechanical properties, *Progress in Materials Science* 53(1) (2008) 1-206.
- [5] C.M. Harris, *Illustrated dictionary of historic architecture*, Courier Corporation 1977.
- [6] G. Fallacara, Toward a stereotomic design: Experimental constructions and didactic experiences, *Proceedings of the Third International Congress on Construction History*, 2009, p. 553.
- [7] A.E. Dien, A Brief Survey of Defensive Armor across Asia, *Journal of East Asian Archaeology* 2(3) (2000) 1-22.
- [8] F. Bouville, E. Maire, S. Meille, B. Van de Moortèle, A.J. Stevenson, S. Deville, Strong, tough and stiff bioinspired ceramics from brittle constituents, *Nature materials* 13(5) (2014) 508-514.
- [9] M. Mirkhalaf, A. Sunesara, B. Ashrafi, F. Barthelat, Toughness by segmentation: Fabrication, testing and micromechanics of architected ceramic panels for impact applications, *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 158 (2019) 52-65.
- [10] M. Mirkhalaf, T. Zhou, F. Barthelat, Simultaneous improvements of strength and toughness in topologically interlocked ceramics, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115(37) (2018) 9128-9133.
- [11] R. Bermejo, Y. Torres, C. Baudin, A. Sánchez-Herencia, J. Pascual, M. Anglada, L. Llanes, Threshold strength evaluation on an Al₂O₃-ZrO₂ multilayered system, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 27(2) (2007) 1443-1448.
- [12] H. Tomaszewski, H. Węglarz, A. Wajler, M. Boniecki, D. Kalinski, Multilayer ceramic composites with high failure resistance, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 27(2) (2007) 1373-1377.

- [13] D. Jianxin, D. Zhenxing, Y. Dongling, Z. Hui, A. Xing, Z. Jun, Fabrication and performance of Al₂O₃/(W, Ti) C+ Al₂O₃/TiC multilayered ceramic cutting tools, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 527(4) (2010) 1039-1047.
- [14] E. Munch, M.E. Launey, D.H. Alsem, E. Saiz, A.P. Tomsia, R.O. Ritchie, Tough, bio-inspired hybrid materials, *Science* 322(5907) (2008) 1516-1520.
- [15] M. Mirkhalaf, B. Ashrafi, A numerical study on improving the specific properties of staggered composites by incorporating voids, *Materials Today Communications* (2017).
- [16] B. Dubus, G. Haw, C. Granger, O. Ledez, Characterization of multilayered piezoelectric ceramics for high power transducers, *Ultrasonics* 40(1) (2002) 903-906.
- [17] S. Gianella, D. Gaia, A. Ortona, High Temperature Applications of SiC Cellular Ceramics, *Advanced Engineering Materials* 14(12) (2012) 1074-1081.
- [18] M. Carlesso, R. Giacomelli, T. Krause, A. Molotnikov, D. Koch, S. Kroll, K. Tushtev, Y. Estrin, K. Rezwan, Improvement of sound absorption and flexural compliance of porous alumina-mullite ceramics by engineering the microstructure and segmentation into topologically interlocked blocks, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 33(13-14) (2013) 2549-2558.
- [19] R. Bermejo, L. Llanes, M. Anglada, P. Supancic, T. Lube, Thermal shock behavior of an Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ multilayered ceramic with residual stresses due to phase transformations, *Key Engineering Materials*, Trans Tech Publ, 2005, pp. 191-198.
- [20] Z. Yin, A. Dastjerdi, F. Barthelat, Tough and deformable glasses with bioinspired cross-ply architectures, *Acta biomaterialia* (2018).
- [21] U.S. Association, ASTM D3763-2006 Standard Test Method for High Speed Puncture Properties of Plastics using Load and Displacement Sensor, USA Standards Association International, USA (2006).